

Targeting Lectin-Mediated Immunosuppression with Tumour-Associated MUC1 O-Glycodomains: Synthesis and Lectin Recognition

Cátia O. Soares,^{1,2} Ana S. Grosso,^{1,2} Helena Coelho,^{1,2} Carlos D. L. Lima,^{1,2} Alejandra Travecedo,^{1,2} David Sánchez-Navarro,³ Irene Ginés Alcober,³ Ramón-Hurtado Guerrero,³ Jesús Jiménez-Barbero,^{5,6} June Ereño-Orbea,^{5,6} & Filipa Marcelo^{1,2}

1. UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal; 2. Associate Laboratory i4HB, Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal; 3. Institute of Biocomputation and Physics of Complex Systems (BIFI), Glycobiology Unit, University of Zaragoza, Mariano Esquillor s/n, Campus Rio Ebro, Edificio I+D, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain. 5. CIC bioGUNE, Basque Research and Technology Alliance, Bizkaia Technology Park, Ed. 800. E-48160, Derio, Spain; 6. Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, Euskadi Plaza 5, 48009 Bilbao, Bizkaia, Spain

ca.soares@campus.fct.unl.pt; filipa.marcelo@fct.unl.pt

Aberrant O-glycosylation of Mucin-1 (MUC1) is a hallmark feature in cancer.¹ In malignancy, MUC1 O-glycans become truncated, due to changes in the expression, location or activity of glycosyltransferases, resulting in new glycan epitopes recognized by lectins.¹ Through this binding event, lectins such as Siglecs, Galectins and MGL, trigger pro-tumour immunological responses and promote metastasis.² Therefore, strategies to disrupt these tumour-glycan/lectin interactions are essential to potentially alleviate anti-tumour immunosuppression and reduce metastasis.

Herein, short MUC1 O-glycodomains that mimic tumour-associated MUC1, were chemoenzymatically synthesized. The products carry different tumour-associated glycans, specifically the Tn antigen (GalNAc α 1O-Ser/Thr) and the sTn antigen (Neu5Ac α 2,6GalNAc α 1O-Ser/Thr), in distinct density schemes (two or five antigens in each of the four tandem repeats). The molecular recognition of these MUC1 O-glycodomains by the lectins Siglec-7 and MGL was investigated using high-resolution NMR, specifically through ¹H,¹⁵N- and ¹H,¹³C-HSQC titrations from the perspective of the ¹³C,¹⁵N-labelled MUC1 O-glycodomains. These structural studies will enhance the understanding of how these types of multivalent ligands are recognized by these lectins, aiding in the selection of the best candidates for future immunological assays to evaluate their potential as immunomodulators.

References

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